

Anomaly Detection In Computer Networks Using Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract— Anomaly detection in computer network is crucial to identify abnormal behaviors that leads to threats or system breakdown. This paper investigates the use of machine learning techniques for network anomaly detection, specifically focusing on three algorithms: Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) from the group of machine learning algorithms were used in this research. In order to assess these algorithms i enriched the set with the most popular gradient boosting models such as XGBoost, LightGBM and CatBoost. Based on such a comparison, we evaluate the advantages and shortcomings of each method in terms of accuracy, computational time spent, and reliability of results in the data on network traffic. I used XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost to my model to determine their preliminary effects on the detection rate.”. This work gives a first look at the possibility of deploying machine learning for practical and efficient network anomaly detection.

Keywords— Anomaly detection, Computer network, machine learning, Random Forest, SVM, K-NN, XGBoost, LightGBM, CatBoost, Network Security.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing reliance on the internet has led to the rapid growth of network traffic, Which makes it a critical area for security and performance monitoring [1]. One of the most unavoidable challenges in modern networks is to identify malicious or abnormal activities which can lead to security concerns , system failures or data leaks [2]. Anomaly detection in network traffic is very important for early detections of systems misconfigurations, insertions and performance issues which might not be immediately indicible but can have long-term consequences. In this research, we propose a machine learning based approach that detects anomalies in network traffic , leveraging both supervised and unsupervised learning methods for identifying deviations from typical behaviour. Network traffic analysis is a process that involves analysis of data traversing the network technologies for abnormal traffic patterns or tendencies that could be part of problems like DoS, intrusion in a network or improper configuration of a system [3]. This is due to the fact that the conventional approaches of anomaly detection are normally dependent on rule-based systems or heuristic models of which are normally very inflexible to the cutting-edge flow traffic. But learning it from scratch or using a bottom-up approach is not very scalable and flexible; on the other hand, Machine learning can learn it from data and identify deviations based on learned representations. However, in this approach, i work with a given dataset containing network traffic information: identifiers of flows and statistical parameters of traffic. In the dataset, there are also columns that are characteristic attributes about the scenario such as numeric measures on data transmission and traffic and labels that point to abnormality. Data cleaning includes preprocessing to fulfill compatibility requirements of machine learning algorithms and feature scaling. Furthermore, methods

such as SMOTE are used in order to tackle the class imbalance problem, thus are important to stabilize the training process of the models on the sparse anomalies. It is, therefore, aimed at identifying relationships between the characteristics of traffic and the presence of anomalies.

In this work, i use a dataset containing numeracy features as well as labeled sample of traffic data including normal and intrusive events. Random Forest, SVM, and KNN models are used to find the relationship between traffic attributes and an anomaly. In the preprocessing step features are normalized by StandardScaler and columns with non-numeric values are dropped for the best modeling. These are then assessed by accuracy, or how many were correctly classified alone to include precision, recall or true positive rate, and F1 score to balance the measure of how many anomalies where correctly detected against the number of false positives and false negatives. Features plotted across the independent variables and dependent variables help in understanding the relationship between independent features while, bar charts, features displayed in form of confusion matrix, and feature importance plots assist in performance metrics.

The findings of this study allow network administrators to minimise possible threats by identifying suspicious traffic in Intrusion Detection Systems. Through this integration of machine learning in the process of network analysis, the efficiency, flexibility and scalability of results are increased to contain security and preserve the integrity of networks.

One of the issues considered in this work concerns enhancing performance of anomaly detection in network traffic based on how to deal with class imbalance. A lot fewer anomalies to normal traffic require more sophisticated preprocessing techniques.

- **SMOTE for Handling Class Imbalance:** This study samples the minority class of anomalies using SMOTE in order to create a balanced data set for training.
- **Data Preprocessing:** Data cleansing and preprocessing like scaling also makes the data ready to use by the machine learning process. To do this, the identifier columns that consist of alphabets and or special characters are omitted.
- **Evaluation Metrics:** In common classification models, metrics such as accuracy, precisions, recollections, as well as F1-score are used to ensure that thorough model's performance evaluation is conducted.

- Model Validation: The Validation is carried out in two folds; fixed train-test split (70-30)% and cross validation to make the model more reliable while being tested on different sectors of the dataset.
- The study utilized six Machine learning models: Random Forest(RF), Support Vector Machines(SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors(KNN), Extreme Gradient Boosting(XGBoost), LightGradient Boosting(LightGBM) and catboost.
- The performance of the models was evaluated by accuracy, precision, recall and the F1 score in order to have a complete picture of models' ability to detect anomalies. To gain more details we used SHAP as a measure for feature importance, Confusion Matrix to test prediction mistakes, Chi-Square as well as Lasso methods to rate features, and ROC-AUC to compare the classification results based on various thresholds.

II. Literature Review

For computer security purpose, anomaly detection is very useful to ensure that a computer network is secure and safe from any type of attacks or from harm. Many of the classical detection techniques, including using signatures, proves ineffective in detecting emerging or emerging variants. Hence it has been realized that machine learning (ML) techniques can provide more flexibility and possibility in identifying abnormalities in the network traffic. This literature review will try to assess the number of machine learning techniques used for anomaly detection in computers networks. The common techniques that are touched throughout the volume contain supervised and unsupervised kinds of learning, and the then common goal is to discuss top approaches to learn the efficiency and strengths and weaknesses of these techniques in practical applications. The review clearly defines the state of the art in existing research, new contributions, and future concerns or contributions in the investigated area.

Amgbara et al. [4] presented a detailed investigation on low-powered machine learning (ML) models for anomaly detection in security of personal IoT devices. Their research evaluated the effectiveness of three popular algorithms: Amongst the classification algorithms there are Decision Trees (DT), k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Support Vector Machines (SVM). Decision Trees emerged top in the detection accuracy at 90%, proving that it is easy to use in solving complicated decision making. KNN gave it a close chase with a correct classification of 88% of the data set; this made use of its abilities to classify data set based on distances to similar data sets. While being less accurate 85%, SVM proved once again that it effectively recognized anomalous activities in the context of IoT environment.. Song wang et al. [5] made a survey on machine learning techniques for anomaly detection in the current and the latest generations of networks; SDNs and IoTs, respectively. Look at how supervised and semi-supervised learning models have been used in the identification of known and

unknown attacks while pointing out that data quality is important when creating a model. Aims to discuss how ML can enhance the efficiency of the detection of anomalous activities in a large scaled network. Focuses on an evaluation of the properties of one or another algorithm and their efficiency depending on the kind of a network and conditions of its functioning.

Shon et al. [6] Proposed an extension Support Vector Machine (SVM) approach for anomaly detection, which deals with deficits of conventional and one-class SVM techniques. Combines unsupervised learning systems such as Self- Organized Feature Map (SOFM), Passive TCP / IP Fingerprinting (PTF), & Genetic Algorithms (GA) to minimize false alarms. Establishes a profile of normal network traffic and utilizes temporal relationship of packet flows for improved identification. Substantiates the approach by experiments on MIT Lincoln Lab and other real-world data sets , where the proposed approach demonstrates better performance over current state-of-art Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS). Abdallah et al. [7] reviewed general and deep learning methods used in the anomaly detection of the cloud networks on DDoS attacks and IDS. Explains different approaches and the datasets used in detection, and evaluates the effectiveness of each. Discusses fundamental issues, such as the limitations of the approach with regards to the scalability and the privacy ones, and future work. This paper aims to enhance the security of the cloud network through developing novel approaches to anomalous behavior identification by employing ML/DL.

Nassif et al. [8] analyzed some current developments in using machine learning approach to network anomaly detection with special emphasis on cloud computing IDS. They consider such models as supervised, unsupervised and hybrid, and analyse the differences of accuracy in terms of intrusion detection. Introduces some of the most used algorithms; include Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Trees, and Neural Networks, amongst others and show that SVM gives the greatest accuracy of 99.91% of on NSL-KDD data set. The paper underscores the idea that hybrid models provide more accurate detection in addition to the fewest false positives, which make it suitable for large networks. Estevez-pereira [9] explored the effectiveness of machine learning algorithms for network anomaly detection employing UNB ISCX IDS 2012 dataset. They evaluate such models as Random Forest, Naive Bayes and Deep Neural Networks (DNN) perform comparative analysis of their effectiveness in terms of detection of network intrusions. The overall best model which was the Random Forest attained a success rate of 99.8% after improving features and performance metrics. The DNN model came next with an accuracy of 99.6%, the Naive Bayes model followed next, after feature adjustment, with an accuracy of 86.9%. The authors perform computation distribution using Apache Structured Streaming, PySpark and MLlib to exploit large-scale data. Consequently, this paper investigates the applicability of risk assessment and network anomaly detection using a machine learning technique, specifically: Random Forest. Elmrabbit et al. [10] described and compared different types of Machine Learning models used to identify anomalous activities in cyber-security, including the CICIDS-2017, UNSW-NB15, and ICS Cyber- Attack datasets. According to the results, the proposed Random Forest (RF) model indicates highest accuracy as compared to other models with 99.9% in CICIDS-2017, 88.5% in UNSW-NB15, and 92.8% in ICS datasets. Though Decision Trees (DT) also

made good predictions, RF was always superior in all measures and hence considered the best algorithm for anomaly detection. R. Sekar et al. [11] presented a hybrid specification-based and anomaly-based approach to network intrusion detection, in an attempt to take advantage of the former's specific accuracy and the latter's broad sensory comprehensiveness. It runs off state-machine specifications of network protocols augmented with statistical data for anomaly identification, and produces less than 10 false positives per day. The concepts make the feature selection process easy and the system works on its own to a very large extent. The performance of the signature set derived from the 1999 Lincoln Labs dataset is valid in different contexts such as detecting probing and denial-of-service attacks and stealthy email viruses.

Liu et al.[12]introduced Opprentice, an intelligent detector selection and parameter tuned anomaly detection framework for unstructured data. In ADs, operators only need to label anomalies, which is after multiple detectors extract features used in training a random forest classifier. Though the assessment of Opprentice was based on the KPIs of a global search engine, it qualified a recall ≥ 0.66 and a precision ≥ 0.66 . It dramatically decreases labeling time (minutes versus days) and provides stable high detection accuracy, so there is no need to tune and select detectors manually. Li et al. [13] looked into the efficiency of using fast machine learning algorithms, namely Decision Trees, Gaussian Naive Bayes, KNN, and SVM for cybersecurity anomaly detection. Decision Trees proved to be more efficient and interpretable than the other modeling techniques for flow datasets resulting to an accuracy of 87% in detection.

Shon et al. [14] proposed a new approach to identify internet attacks based on machine learning techniques GA for features selection and SVM for packet classification. It compares three SVM approaches: , and an Enhanced SVM soft margin SVM supervised, one-class SVM unsupervised and an enhanced SVM. The best detector is the Enhanced SVM with a sigmoid kernel which received a detection accuracy of 94.65%, but several difficulties: overdetermination and high number of false positives. It also explains how the integration of supervised and unsupervised systems can enhance performance while at the same time detecting new attacks. R.Kumari et al. [15] proposed the application of K-means clustering and Apache Spark in realizing network intrusions via unsupervised ML. It overcomes the drawback of the signature-based systems for identifying new, unknown types of attack by monitoring traffic. K-means clustering categorizes similar points and aids in identifying an anomaly in the data pattern, as a result of which the system is scalable and optimized. It is demonstrated how the approach is actually good at identifying unknown attacks and is more effective than using the conventional methods.

Hasan et al. [16] compressed SVM and RF classifiers for intrusion detection using the KDD'99 set. It thus tackles the problem of duplicate records within the dataset to develop improved versions of the dataset that shows such

records (KDD99Train+ and KDD99Test+). The study reveals that if the accuracy of the two classifiers is compared, the error rate of the proposed system based on the SVM is lower but it can be moderately well done on the RF classifier which is less time consuming. The results on IDS obtained by both classifiers increase the accuracy of the system and decrease the number of false negatives, which could be interesting for improving IDS. G.Prashanth et al. [17] analyzed the selection of features and the tuning of parameters in RF for NIDS. Compared with the traditional rule-based systems, the RF provides a flexible, time-dependent solution for the application of intrusion detection. However, it has several drawbacks of supervised anomaly detection including high false positives based on changing network behavior patterns. This paper also demonstrates the applicability of unsupervised outlier detection in RF to attain better accuracy for NIDS because RF does not require attack- free training data.

Virkram et al. [18] discussed the aspect of anomaly detection in particular through the Isolation Forest algorithm applied to the network traffic as more and more industries are experiencing growth in their cyber-attacks due to IoT and wireless devices. Of the investigated approaches, the study concentrates on the ability to apply unsupervised machine learning for identifying the outliers in the network traffic with the use of KDD dataset. Isolation Forest is selected since it performs well in dealing with imbalanced data and requires no attack-free datasets for identifying anomalies. In addition, the paper discusses the preprocessing steps for data cleaning and dimensionality shrinking through the PCA analysis in addition to the accuracy test as well as the decision functions. Kumar et al. [19] made an intelligent hybrid model that integrates Decision Trees (DT), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) that separately provided high rates of anomaly detection in network security. Using these algorithms, this study was able to harness Decision Trees; interpretability and speed, KNNs pattern recognition; and SVMs boundary-based classification. The proposed transitional ensemble indeed achieved higher improvement of detection rates, with up to 90 percent accuracy in identifying anomalies especially in more complicated and elaborate forms of cyber-attacks. The efficiency and reliability of this integration were shown in an increase of accuracy, as well as in the ability to perform even faster in the case of different kinds of attacks, making it one of the most suitable solutions for applying in real-time applications in network security. The research also shows that combining different models improves the reliability of intrusion detection while using a single type of model is not nearly as effective.

I. Methodology

This section contains a detailed description of the methods used and the working processes in this research. The working methodology is divided into six main parts: Data Collection, data preprocessing, data splitting, feature extraction with data division, ML classifiers, assessment metrics. The directions of work are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig 1: Our working Flow consist of these following methods

Data Collection

In this paper the dataset used for anomaly detection on computer networks was downloaded from Figshare platform and has 29,761 records and 92 fields. Usually, each row of the file is a record that contains information related to network traffic activities such raw data sizes, virtual addresses and other traits of sections like Text, Data and Resource. The variable Type is the target variable since it differentiates normal and anomalous activity in the network. Because of the disparity between genuine and unusual samples, data pre processing methods for handling missing values and removing the duplicates were implemented on the dataset. Thus, this high- dimensional imbalanced dataset is suitable for assess machine learning algorithms including Random forest, SVM, and kNN for the detection of anomalous traffic in networks.

Data preprocessing

In this research, the following steps were performed on the dataset in order to preprocess it before training and testing. The first step was to pre cleaned the data where spaces and special characters were removed from the column heading. This made it easy to label the columns of the dataframe appropriately and easy when the researcher is analyzing the data. After completing the name of the columns, I checked the confirmation of the target variable, where ‘Type’ column will differentiate between normal and anomalous network traffic.

The next step was the splitting of the target variable from the feature set. The resulting dataset contains only two columns: ‘Type,’ which corresponds to the labels (normal or anomalous), was extracted as the target variable. The rest of the columns, which included several sizes as raw data, virtual address, some characteristics of sections as the input features, they remain and were analyzed . Another column, SHA256, present but not of numeric type, was also eliminated: it is a file hash that does not inform a numeric algorithm, such as machine learning.

Fig-2 : Data Spitting visualization

As the next step for the data preparation and since the present dataset has a number of features, it was also important to scale the same. Standardisation was done using StandardScaler from scikit-learn which standardizes the features to have geometric mean zero and unit standard deviation. This helps to make the features more distinguishable as they suit the machine learning algorithm in a way because the Machine Learning Models Is less Dependent on the scales. The scaler was applied on the training information and also the same sort was used on the check details to evade leakage.

After that, due to the fact that the ratio of normal instances to anomalous instances in the data set is fairly large, SMOTE was used to balance the data set out. SMOTE is a technique for synthesizing samples from the minority class into two or more new and different samples by adding new dimensions to the current samples space. From this process, the performance of the machine learning models can be enhanced from the aspect that during the training, the model will successfully be trained with both classes of samples, which greatly avoids the situation where the model will have too much prejudice towards one type of sample.

Model Selectin

As one of the machine learning techniques for detecting anomalous behavior in computer networks, Random Forest is adopted in this paper. Random Forest is an extension of the basic decision-tree algorithm, where during training more decision trees are created and their results are then combined in order to avoid high variance. Every tree in the forest makes a prediction and the final decision is made depending on how many trees in a forest were of the same opinion – in the case of classification or depending on the average– in the case of regression. In anomaly detection case, the model work as follows, trees are trained on different subsets of data extracted from the network traffic data. In testing process, Random Forest assigns new instances as normal or anomalous based on inferred patterns. The model performs well in terms of scalability, nonlinear patterns, and workload imbalance, which makes it suitable for accurately identifying emerging and infrequent network abnormalities or invasions in real-time, not driven by the majority events.

Here in this paper SVM is used for the detection of anomaly in computer networks where It has provided a very effective technique for classification of the network traffic either as normal or anomalous. SVM is a method of supervised learning which performs classification by finding the hyperplane that maximally separates two or more linearly separable classes of data. For binary classification, SVM focuses on maximizing a distance between two classes of data, normal class and anomalous class. As applied to anomaly detection SVM works on labelled data where training is to identify a boundary that would separate the normal behavior from the potentially anomalous behavior even if the former is riddled with perturbation and is non-linear. The one-class SVM variant is particularly valuable for anomaly detection because it assumes that the dataset is dominated by the normal class and learns only its boundary; any point falling outside this boundary is considered anomalous. SVM is ideally suited for high dimensionality and foreign kernel functions for non-linear decision boundaries, hence the tool of choice for studying sophisticated and subtle intrusions in a computer network.

The third machine learning model used in this paper is the k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) algorithm where kNN is a simple powerful instance based learning algorithm that classify an instance according to the similarity measured using the distance of the nearest neighbors in the feature space. While learning

phase, kNN retains all training data instances and makes a decision in classify new data points based on distance computation of the 'k' nearest neighbors. The class label of the nearest majority mean class among the neighbours is selected as the class label for the new point. In anomaly detection, kNN works with recognizing the instances that are distant from their neighbors which is to say that they do not fit well in the patterns seen in normal network traffic. kNN is a non-parametric, lazy learning algorithm, which does not iii training to build a model, but uses a training set to make prediction when tested. It is very suitable for use in the identification of outliers However it may be influenced by the value of k, the distance metric used as well as dimensionality and scale of data set used unless these have been optimized appropriately.

This work uses XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost models to evaluate the efficiency of the initial anomaly detection algorithms which are RF, SVM, and kNN. These three models are gradient boosting algorithms that bring efficient massive data handling of large volumes of professional data and more precise predictions.

- Popular machine learning algorithm, XGBoost or Extreme Gradient Boosting is an efficient and scalable boost of gradient, which uses multiple weak learner models for overall performance. It is especially useful in classification problems and works well with imbalance data set, so it could be used for comparison of accuracy and stability between chosen algorithms – RF, SVM, kNN.
- LightGBM another gradient boosting model which is built for high efficiency. It organizes layers as 'leaf wise' rather than 'layer wise': this means that the training time results to be faster and precise in situations where large data sets are involved. To compare the computational efficiency and detection accuracy of the primary algorithms, LightGBM was applied in this study.
- CatBoost or Categorical Boosting is the gradient boosting model which is better performing in cases with categorical data with the usage of ordered boosting and improved categorical features treatment. RF was found to provide high performance with no adjustments other than standard scaling and was used here to see how complex real world datasets affect the performance of the three methods: RF, SVM and kNN.

These models were not used for direct anomaly detection but were employed to evaluate and compare the efficacy of the three basic algorithms, thereby offering further understanding into their measurement potential and speed.

III. Performance and Evaluation Metrics

In this study, the performance of the anomaly detection models is evaluated using multiple standard metrics: In this work accuracy, precision, Recall and F1 Score is used for the evaluation of the model. Accuracy is used to evaluate the general performance of the model, or in other words, the model is able to predict how many of the times the answer given by the model is correct. Precision and Recall explain the relative efficiency of the model in terms of correct anomalous instances detection, while Precision reflects the share of positive predictions that are actually anomalous and Recall is the model's ability to identify all the existing anomalous instances. Due to the capability of using both precision and recall the F1 Score, that is the harmonic mean between the two is more suited especially for cases of imbalanced datasets. These evaluation metrics are therefore important in revealing the

strengths and limitations of the models in detecting network anomalies and guaranteeing a credible and sound detection procedure.

Accuracy: Accuracy refers to the overall rate of true positive and true negatives sum total of the total positives in all of the cases. It is simply an average measure of accuracy as it shows how well the model has tested across different classes. However, these metrics do not give the whole picture in cases with imbalanced data; most of the time, the model will predict the majority class.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$$

Precision: Precision determines the percentage of the true positive cases among all the positive cases classified by the model (that is, among all anomalies detected). Here many high precision is indicated because the model is able to adequately identify the anomalies without labelling many normal instances as anomalous. Some scenarios are better served by high precision more so where the cost of a false positive is high such as in networks with lots of alerts that may prove costly to sort out.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

Recall : Recall defines how accurately the model identifies all the anomalies present in the given data set (which means how many of them were actually found). Recall is highly relevant in anomaly detection because failure to alert of an attack or an anomaly (false negative) can be disastrous to the security of an organization. High recall means that most of the real anomalies are flagged although it is likely to produce more false alarms.

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

F1-Score: The F1 Score is the average of Precision and Recall; both scores form the F1 Score, which gives a single score with the best of both worlds. It is especially useful when it comes to the evaluation of the outcomes of uneven data distributions because it takes into account both the Accuracy of the anomaly detection as a measure of precision and the ability of the model to identify anomalies of concern as measured by the recall factor. However, when there is a trade-off in the Precision and the Recall then the F1 Score offers a better view of the performance of the models.

$$F1 - \text{score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

IV. Result Analysis

In this section, compared the results of Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) model in the detection of anomaly traffic. To evaluate these models further, the use of XGBoost, LightGBM and CatBoost were performed. These boosting algorithms were used to measure the impact of incorporating the boosting algorithms with the base models. This is done in order to determine how the integration of these boosting techniques impacted the overall performance, particularly in the detection of anomalies, the class imbalance issue, and the complexity of the data. The results are useful in comprehending how other algorithms, viz boosting, can supplement traditional models for anomaly detection in computer networks.

Table 1: Represents the performance results of applied models without data balancing. When comparing the

models at the initial stage, Random Forest showed the best results with 80.80% for accuracy, 81.31% for precision, 80.80% for recall, and 80.94 overall F1-score, which also proves good and balanced performance of anomalies detection. For Support Vector Machine (SVM), the results were smooth with an accuracy of 67.13 percent, with precision and recall both at 68.55 percent and an F1-score of 64.93 percent and therefore significantly poorer performance compared to Random Forest. Further, k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) still came out as quite balanced with an accuracy of 76.99 percent, precision and recall both at 77. In sum, Random Forest is the most stable and accurate to ensure the highest efficiency when the models were evaluated in the first step.

Table 1: Performance evaluation result without data balancing

Algorithm Name	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
RF	80	81	80	80
SVM	67	68	67	64
KNN	76	77	76	77

Fig-2: Here we can see the result comparison between Random Forest, SVM and KNN without data balancing

Fig 3: Confusion matrix before balancing dataset for RF, SVM and KNN

Table 2 : Represents the accuracy after applying SMOTE. When class imbalance was compensated through SMOTE, the efficiency of the models was reassessed. Random forest maintained its good results for the balanced detection with accuracy 80.80%, the precision of 81.31% and recall of 80.80% as well as F1-score 80.94%. SVM got better results than before: accuracy was 67.13%, the precision was 68.55%, the recall was 67.13%, and the F1 score was 64.93% that is, handling with minority class anomalous data better than before; kNN got balanced results: The accuracy was 76.99%, the precision was 77.39%, the recall was 76.99%, and the F1 In general, SMOTE gave a better position for the models in detecting anomalies fully, but still, the Random Forest demonstrated the highest scores for accuracy and the F1-score.

Table 2: Performance evaluation result after balancing data using SMOTE

Algorithm Name	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
RF	80	81	80	80
SVM	49	65	49	45
KNN	75	76	75	76

Table 3: The above models were retested after the cross-validation had been performed on them. Random Forest had 80.31% accuracy, 80.80% precision, 80.31% recall with 80.47% F1-score confirming enhanced and balanced anomaly detection capacity. For Support Vector Machine (SVM), the performance was observed to be poor with accuracy of only 49.99%, precision, recall and F1-score was 66.29%, 49.99% respectively showing that it has a poor ability to detect anomalies as compared to other models Random Forest's KNN had an accuracy of 76.10%, precision 76.90%, recall 76.10% and F1-score of Thus, the Random Forest algorithm was the best performer while the SVM model did worst; the kNN model was moderate.

Table 3 : Model evaluation after cross validation

Algorithm Name	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
RF	80	80	80	80
SVM	49	66	49	46
KNN	76	76	76	76

Table 4 : This table represents the value after applying the XGBoost. These results imply that XGBoost did not increase performance improvements in instances for Random Forest, SVM, or kNN in this study. The low accuracy obtained for all models points towards one or multiple of these factors making it difficult to determine whether or not XGBoost was effective in boosting their performance for this specific anomaly detection problem.

Table 4: Model evaluation after applying XGBoost

Algorithm Name	Accuracy (%)
RF	18
SVM	18
KNN	18

Fig 4: Model Comparison graph with XGBoost accuracy

Table 5 : After applying LightGBM, the models showed the following results: Using Random Forest, the best result was obtained with accuracy of 81.28%, precision of 79.42%, recall of 80.09 % and F1 – score of 79.60 Of all the methods applied, Random Forest has the best training time of 10.91 sec. For the model: Support Vector Machine (SVM) the accuracy achieved was 64.68 % precision 65.12 % recall 65.75% F1 score 60.70% and the training time was 64.16 seconds For the model k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) the result obtained was 77.70%

accuracy, precision 75.19 %, recall 76.60 %, F1 score The result shown that LightGBM has the best performance by achieving the highest accuracy of 82,14% and higher precision, recall 80,85%, 81,53% respectively, an F1 score of 80,78 with a relatively low training time of 5.18sec. In general, LightGBM was slightly more accurate as compared to the other two algorithms while Random Forest gave slightly better precision than LightGBM with a longer training period as compared to LightGBM.

Table 5: Model evaluation with LightGBM

Algorithm Name	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
RF	81	79	80	79
SVM	64	65	65	60
KNN	77	75	76	75

Table 5: After applying CatBoost, the performance of the models was as follows: Random Forest detected anomalies with 16.62% accuracy, 52.57% precision, 16.62% recall and F1- score of 7.58% which clearly showed poor results in the detection of anomalies. SVM's performance in terms of accuracy was 16.50%, while the precision was 86.22%, that although was not good in terms of detecting anomalies the model had high precision but low recall and F1-score of 4.67%,for kNN, the accuracy was 17.86% with precision of 68.99%, and a recall 17.86%, and a low F1-score of 9.99 For CatBoost, the analysis of the data set provided accuracy as 18.73%, precision as 55.38%, recall as 18.73%, and F1-score of 10.53%which was marginally better than kNN in predicting the anomalies. As shown above, all models struggled to present higher accuracy and F1-score, meaning that anomaly detection in this dataset remains a concern at the moment.

Table 5: Model evaluation with CatBoost

Algorithm Name	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
RF	16	52	16	7
SVM	16	86	16	4
KNN	17	68	17	9

Fig 5: Model performance through Confusion Matrix

Fig-8 : In this study, ROC AUC curve was employed in the visualization aspect to consider the performance level of the anomaly detection models in the discrimination of normal and anomalous traffic. The AUC values give a very clear picture as to how well the model is doing for different classes. In the output, each Class represents the type of anomaly detection it belongs to and their corresponding AUC which shows how well the model differentiates that class from others. The AUC values reported for each class were as follows: Class 1 AUC: 0.9616 Class 2 AUC: 0.9888 Class 3 AUC: 0.9999 Class 4 AUC: 0.9477 Class 5 AUC: 0.9801 Class 6 AUC: 0.9390 Class 7 AUC: 0.9451 These AUC scores pay prove that the model yields an almost perfect performance on most of the classes, especially Class 3 which had 0.999 AUC, and class 2 which had 0.9888 AUC, proving strong discriminative power between normal and anomalous instances in those classes. Yet, the Defogged Multi-class model has slightly worse performance for Class 6 as 0.9390 and Class 4 as 0.9477 while these values are still relatively high.

VI. Conclusion

This paper aims to review the machine learning methods for the detection of anomaly in computer networks; some of the methods are Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM) and k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), with all advanced models like as XGBoost, LightGBM, CatBoost. Preprocessing the data in this study using feature scaling and SMOTE for class imbalance improved the performance of the model. From the results we can see that Random Forest has the highest accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score; LightGBM shows high efficiency and competitive accuracy with a small number of features. But CatBoost and XGBoost exhibited only a small gain, which could be attributed to its inherent dataset-specific issues. The construction of such tools such as SHAP for feature

importance as well as ROC-AUC for the evaluation made the model more interpretable and discriminative. Nevertheless, issues arise when working with large and unbalanced datasets, as well as enhancing precision when it matters most. Overall, this study reveals that machine learning is a promising approach to achieving accurate, high-throughput intrusion detection to be built upon and expanded in future work incorporating hybrid models and deep learning paradigms to tackle more emergent network threats.

VII. References

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